

Book of abstracts

2nd Debrecen Online Conference on Infectious Diseases in a One Health Context (DOCIDOH)

18th-20th June, 2025 - Online

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Preface

The One Health approach has established itself as an important tool for the investigation, surveillance and containment of infectious diseases. Human and veterinary pathogens can spread across multiple hosts and the environment, creating complex and often poorly understood transmission networks or driving evolutionary events that lead to the emergence or re-emergence of novel or neglected infectious diseases. These include foodborne, waterborne and vector-borne diseases, as well as the hidden epidemic of antimicrobial resistance – all of which pose a major challenge to healthcare, the economy and society and require urgent attention. The 1st DOCIDOH brought together physicians, veterinarians, environmentalists, epidemiologists, molecular biologists, ecologists and various other experts to discuss issues related to One Health.

As a follow-up to the first DOCIDOH and to promote discussion and knowledge exchange, the One Health Institute of the Faculty of Health Sciences, the Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Environmental Management and the Department of Metagenomics of the University of Debrecen announces the second Debrecen Online Conference on Infectious Diseases in a One Health context (DOCIDOH), which will take place from 18 to 20 June 2025.

The conference aims at attracting researchers in the topics:

- **antimicrobial resistance in a One Health perspective**
- **alternatives to antimicrobials in human and veterinary medicine**
- **genomic epidemiology of pathogens across sectors**
- **emerging and re-emerging diseases and vectors**
- **parasites ecology**
- **ecology of infections, environmental DNA and environmental health**
- **bioinformatic tools for One Health research**
- **food safety and foodborne diseases**
- **social perceptions of antibiotics and their alternatives (e.g. phage therapy, vaccination)**

On the conference website (<https://konferencia.unideb.hu/en/docidoh25>), participants will find up-to-date information during the event, such as the detailed program and online access links to the sessions and breakout rooms.

Organizing and scientific committee

- **Dr. Gábor Kardos – One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen**
- **Dr. Csongor Freytag – One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen**
- **Dr. Dalma Papp – One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen**
- **Dr. Enikő Fehér – Department of Microbiology and Infectious Diseases, University of Veterinary Medicine Budapest**
- **Dr. Eszter Kaszab – Department of Microbiology and Infectious Diseases, University of Veterinary Medicine Budapest**
- **Lilla Buzgó – One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen**
- **Vivien Nagy – One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen**
- **Dr. Krisztina Szarka – One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen**
- **Dr. Levente Laczkó – One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen**
- **Dr. Pálfyné Dr. Nóra Vass – Department of Animal Husbandry, Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Environmental Management, University of Debrecen**
- **Dr. Renáta Knop – Department of Animal Husbandry, Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Environmental Management, University of Debrecen**
- **Dr. Márta Vargha – National Centre for Public Health and Pharmacy; One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen**
- **Flórián Sipos – Institute of Metagenomics, University of Debrecen**

The program at a glance

June 18.

8:30 (CET) 09:00 (CET) Conference Opening

Orsolya Surján, Szabolcs Pásztor, Anita Rusinné Fedor

I. Section: Antimicrobial resistance in a One Health perspective

09:00 (CET) 09:30 (CET) Semi-Plenary

Erika Tóth: Environmental monitoring of AMR in the River Danube: the missing piece of the One Health puzzle

09:30 (CET) 10:15 (CET) Regular talks

Chair: Gábor Kardos

Andrea Szabó: Barriers and possibilities: One Health concept in the Hungarian antimicrobial stewardship

Randa Bazzi: The role of veterinarians in the One Health approach to antimicrobial resistance perspectives in Jordan

Isma Benmazouz: Antimicrobial resistance in Wild birds: Birds as AMR reservoirs and disseminators

10:15 (CET) 10:30 (CET) Break

10:30 (CET) 11:15 (CET) Regular talks

Chair: Gábor Kardos

Patrik Mag: Antimicrobial susceptibility of *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* isolates from canine dermatitis in Hungary

Ádám Kerek: Phenotypic and Genotypic Characterization of Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) Production in Commensal *Escherichia coli* St

Szilveszter Csorba: The role of environmental factors in the spread of antimicrobial resistance in the poultry production chain

11:15 (CET) 12:00 (CET) Lunch Break

12:00 (CET) 13:00 (CET) Regular Talks

Chair: Márta Vargha

Máté Farkas: Antibiotic resistance patterns in relation to biosecurity measures and antibiotic use based on data from pig farms

Delia-Liliana Nicoară: Antibiotic-resistant *Klebsiella* spp. form a Preventive Medicine Approach: a review

Balázs Seres: Investigating the spread of antibiotic resistance using wastewater-based epidemiology

Lilla Buzgó: Comparative genomic epidemiology of multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* within the One Health approach

13:00 (CET) 13:15 (CET) Break

II. Section: Emerging and re-emerging diseases and vectors

13:15 (CET) 13:45 (CET) Semi-Plenary

Gianvito Lanave: Decoding the viral code: 25 years of virus discovery in Bari

13:45 (CET) 15:00 (CET) Regular Talks

Chair: Nóra Vass

Anna Pataki: CRESS DNA virus surveillance in wild birds

Barbara Igriczi: Prevalence and genetic characterization of porcine rotavirus A in Hungarian pig farms

Fruzsina Tóth: Genomic characterization of novel protoparvoviruses in domestic ruminants in Hungary

Zalán Homonnay: Isolation and whole-genome characterization of Batai virus (Orthobunyavirus) from a cattle farm in Hungary

Dóra Máté: Surveillance of coronaviruses with a novel broad-spectrum detection system

15:00 (CET) 15:15 (CET) Break

15:15 (CET)

16:30 (CET)

Regular Talks

Chair: Krisztina Szarka

Fatima Ezzohra Ezahedi: Tracing SARS-CoV-2 Evolution in Algeria: Insights from 2020–2023

Muhammad Muhsin Umar: Dengue outbreaks in northern Nigeria: Evaluating the recommended Takeda vaccine and future prevention strategies

Gabor Toth: Blood donors as sentinels for genomic surveillance of West Nile virus in Germany

Boglárka Pollák: Wastewater-based epidemiological surveillance of respiratory pathogens

Levente Zsichla: Molecular epidemiology of the HIV-1 epidemic in Hungary until 2024

June 19.

II. Section: Emerging and re-emerging diseases and vectors

08:30 (CET) 09:00 (CET) Semi-Plenary

09:00 (CET) 09:45:00 (CET) Regular Talks

Chair: Renáta Knop

Tamara Szentivanyi: The evolution of mosquito and mosquito-borne disease monitoring in Hungary: past, present, future

Nikoletta Andrea Nagy: Genome of *Aedes koreicus* and the importance of vector genetics

Kristína Hudáková: Molecular detection of *Anaplasma* spp. in wild animals in Eastern Slovakia

Randa Bazzi: A Comprehensive Comparative Risk Analysis of Livestock Slaughterhouse Operations in Jordan and Argentina: A One Health Perspective

09:45 (CET) 10:00 (CET) Break

III. Section: Food safety and foodborne diseases

10:00 (CET) 11:15 (CET) Regular Talks

Chair: Erzsébet Némedi

Eszter Virág: Advancing Biofungicide Strategies to Ensure Healthy Crop Production

Sarita Romani: Inhibition of *Botrytis cinerea* mycelial growth by soluble and volatile metabolite and plant promoting activity in tomatoes seed

Miroslav Urosevic: The importance of biosecurity measures in cyprinid fish ponds: the preliminary results from Bosnia and Herzegovina

Éva Laslo: Foodborne Pathogens in Cheese: Their Origins, Risks, and One Health Relevance

Ali Aljeratly: Multi-Element Profiling and Health Risk Assessment of Commercial Tahini Products using ICP-OES

11:15 (CET) 12:00 (CET) Lunchbreak

12:00 (CET) 12:45 (CET) Regular Talks

Chair: Károly Pál

Rozalia-Veronika Salamon: Investigation of the soaking of matured semi-hard cheeses in blackcurrant wine or in natural blackcurrant juice

Krisztina Pócsik-Sáfrány: Risk factors for spinach consumption and how to improve them

Eyesun Naammo: Effect of Chitosan Coating on Healthy and Infected Walnuts

12:45 (CET) 13:00 (CET) Break

13:00 (CET) 15:00 (CET) Regular Talks

Chair: Gyula Kasza

Cristina Popovici: Designing novel plant-based cheese-like product using walnuts: insights from color and texture parameters

Cristina Popovici: Plant-based yoghurt: a promising sustainable alternative to dairy products

Roland Sipos: Using management approaches and plant-based feed supplements in large-scale pig farms as alternative solutions to weaning

András Bittsánszky: Effectiveness of food safety self-checking systems in Hungarian school catering

Zsuzsa Farkas: CONTEMFOOD Project: Contaminants in Meat Replacement Products: A Contemporary Food Safety Perspective

Arthur Muhoro: Recent research efforts on the detection of agrochemicals in honey and honey products in Kenya.

Gyöngyvér Boglárka Péterffy: Evaluating the Antimicrobial Properties of Purslane (*Portulaca oleracea* L.) Extracts Against Clinically Relevant Pathogens

Loránd Alexa: Pseudocereals in beer production: Investigation of quality, nutritional value and chemical safety

June 20.

IV. Section: Alternatives to antimicrobials in human and veterinary medicine

08:30 (CET) 09:00 (CET) Semi-Plenary

Lars Fieseler: Bacteriophages for the control of the fire blight pathogen *Erwinia amylovora*

09:00 (CET) 09:30 (CET) Regular Talks

Chair: Gábor Kardos

Marcell Gulyás: Bacteriophages against antibiotic-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains

Evelin Szoták: Isolation and characterization of *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* infecting bacteriophages

09:30 (CET) 09:45 (CET) Break

V. Section: Social perceptions of antibiotics and their alternatives

09:45 (CET) 11:15 (CET) Regular Talks

Chair: Éva Kertész

Gergely Pethő: AI-Supported Discourse Analysis of Vaccine Skepticism in a Post-Truth Context

Ágnes Hajdu: Behavioural Drivers of Hand Hygiene: Early Results from the EU JAMRAI 2 WP7.4 Hungarian Pilot Study Using the COM-B Model

Éva Libicki: Left Behind in Health: The Consequences of Digital Disconnection and Limited Support

Flórián Sipos: Towards Responsible Antibiotic Use: Progress Report on a Participatory Research Project in Primary Care

Gerda Holló: Sequencing method optimized for monitoring microbiome changes in burn patients

Delia Costache: Anaphylactic reaction secondary to surgically treated hydatid cyst: a case report

11:15 (CET) 11:30 (CET) Conference Closing

Gábor Kardos: Concluding remarks

11:30 (CET) 12:30 (CET) Lunchbreak

12:30 (CET)

13:30 (CET)

Breakout Rooms

Breakout rooms on the following topics:

- **Current and future directions in phage research and applications**
- **Future infectious threats: the need for preparedness**
- **Veterinary science as an integral part of One Health**

For the detailed program see the conference website:

<https://konferencia.unideb.hu/en/program-2nd-debrecen-online-conference-infectious-diseases-one-health-context-docidoh>

Abstracts

Invited Talks

Section I – Antimicrobial Resistance in a One Health Perspective

Environmental Monitoring of AMR in the River Danube: the Missing Piece of the One Health Puzzle

Erika Tóth¹, Judit Makk¹, Alexander Kirschner³, Iris Schachner-Groehs³, Ádám Goschi¹, Bernadett Khayer², Márta Vargha²

¹ Department of Microbiology, ELTE, Budapest, Hungary

² National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy, Budapest, Hungary

³ Institute of Hygiene and Applied Immunology, Medical University of Vienna, Austria

The environmental transmission and spread of AMR in surface waters and the impact of communal wastewater as potential source of AMR are receiving increasing attention. Together with several environmental parameters different AMR genes (*intI1*, *sul1*, *qnrS*, *tetM*, *blaTEM*, *blaOXA-48like*, *blaCTX M-1* group, *blaKPC*, *blaCTX M-9* group) were tested by qPCR in a longitudinal and a temporal monitoring during Joint Danube Survey 4. Multivariate analysis indicated that for both the longitudinal and the temporal sample set, predominantly human origin faecal pollution was the most significant driver of AMR occurrence in the Danube River. Vancomycin resistant Enterococci as well as 3rd generation cephalosporin resistant coliform bacteria were enumerated upstream and downstream of Budapest by cultivation. Results has shown that the CFU values of resistant coliform/*E. coli* are significantly higher downstream Budapest than at the upstream region. In biofilms developing downstream Budapest AMR genes were not detected but critical levels of faecal pollution in the water were associated with increased relative abundance of *Sphaerotilus*. High quantity of VRE (e.g. *Enterococcus faecium* – most have *vanA* type resistance) and meropenem resistant coliform bacteria (e.g. *Citrobacter braakii* – with sporadically occurring OXA-48, CTX-M-1 group genes) were isolated and identified from the wastewater of North, Central and South WWTPs of Budapest – all three are discharging treated wastewater into the Danube.

We thank the organizers of the JDS4 and the ELTE Thematic Excellence Programme 2020.

Section II – Emerging and re-emerging diseases and vectors

Decoding the Viral Code: 25 Years of Virus Discovery in Bari

Gianvito Lanave¹

¹ Department of Veterinary Medicine, University of Bari Aldo Moro, Bari, Italy

Virus discovery is a rapidly expanding field in modern virology, essential to understanding viral biodiversity and preventing future epidemics. The advent of novel sequencing technologies, metagenomic approaches, and advanced bioinformatics tools has allowed the identification of previously unknown viruses in a wide range of environments and hosts. The starting point for the discovery of new viruses is often the clinic, chiefly in the presence of clinical signs or syndromes with unknown etiology. An example of this approach in our laboratories is represented by the discovery in 2024 of a human parvovirus B19 analog (Erythroparvovirus) in feral cats in Italy. The cats were also positive for Domestic cat hepadnavirus (DCH), a hepatitis B virus (HBV) analog, discovered in 2018 in Australia. For genome sequencing and for metaviromic, sequence-independent methods, based on random amplification of viral nucleic acids can be used. For circular DNA viruses, a cost-effective, unbiased sequence-independent enrichment (USIE) strategy, based on rolling circle amplification (RCA), is preferred. These strategies can be applied to several massive sequencing platforms. Also, for large collections of samples, panviral protocols (PCR and RT-PCR) are more suitable. These protocols have been used alone or in combination in our laboratories to investigate the genetic diversity and evolution of animal viruses.

Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca, PRIN 2022 “Investigating Hepatotropic Viruses in carnivores and humans in a One Health perspective” (HVOH) prot. 2022EPP2TT.

Section II – Emerging and re-emerging diseases and vectors

The Evolution of Mosquito and Mosquito-borne Disease Monitoring in Hungary: Past, Present, Future

Tamara Szentivanyi¹

¹ Institute of Ecology and Botany, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Budapest, Hungary

Invasive mosquitoes and mosquito-borne diseases are an increasing concern in Europe, driven by climate change, globalization, and ecological shifts. In response, the Hungarian Mosquito Monitor Program (mosquitosurveillance.hu) was launched in 2019 to establish a comprehensive, nationwide surveillance network. Aligned with both the One Health and One Biosecurity approaches, the program integrates real-time data collection, disease surveillance efforts, and citizen engagement in detecting threats posed by invasive species. This program relies heavily on citizen science participation to understand patterns in mosquito and pathogen distribution. Using mosquito occurrence data, our program generates regularly updated risk maps of invasive mosquitoes, which can be used to improve mosquito control efforts and reveal regions with higher epidemiological risk. These maps, combined with ongoing public education efforts, improve both local and national capacity to respond to vector-borne disease threats. Besides invasive mosquito monitoring, the program conducts mosquito-borne pathogen screening in vertebrate hosts based on citizen science-provided data and samples, offering critical insights into potential reservoirs and transmission dynamics. This work aims to offer an overview of past and present findings from the program and highlighting its potential as a scalable model for cross-border surveillance and One Health-based interventions.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to László Z. Garamszegi, principal investigator of the presented project and General Director of the HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research. I am also thankful to the members of our group, the Evolutionary Ecology Research Group, as well as our national and international collaborators, whose ongoing contributions of data, insights, and research infrastructure have been invaluable. Finally, we extend our deepest appreciation to the citizen science participants, without whom the studies presented here would not have been possible.

Section IV – Alternatives to antimicrobials in human and veterinary medicine

Bacteriophages for the Control of the Fire Blight Pathogen *Erwinia amylovora*

Lars Fieseler¹

¹ Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Zurich, Switzerland

Erwinia amylovora is a member of the Erwiniaceae and the causative agent of fire blight, a severe disease of Rosaceae plants. It spreads through the xylem of an infected plant and produces exopolysaccharides (EPS), e.g., a capsule, which leads to ooze formation and canker development. Transposon mutagenesis of *E. amylovora* revealed that adsorption of the T7-like phage L1 and the SP6-like phage S2 is dependent on amylovoran synthesis. Both phages exhibit a Depolymerase (Dpo). DpoL1 specifically binds to amylovoran and cleaves the galactose backbone. Adsorption of phage S6 (Schitoviridae) and the FO1-like phage M7 depends on the bacterial cellulose. Infective S6 virions degraded cellulose to glucose molecules and Gp95, a phage encoded cellulase, is involved to catalyze the reaction. In vitro application of DpoL1 together with the capsule-independent phage Y2 (Chaseviridae) revealed a strong synergistic inhibitory effect and caused a 4 log reduction of viable cell counts. Y2 is highly specific to *E. amylovora* and solely relies on LPS for adsorption. Transposon mutagenesis revealed four so far unrecognized genes in *E. amylovora*, which play a central role in both, LPS and/or EPS synthesis. Deletion of each gene affected either LPS or EPS composition and resulted in highly reduced adsorption and efficacy of plating not only for Y2, but also for other phages that infect *E. amylovora*. Mutants were highly attenuated in virulence on detached blossoms."

This work was funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNF) grant 310030_156947.

**Section I – Antimicrobial Resistance in a One Health Perspective
Contributed Talks**

Barriers and Possibilities: One Health Concept in the Hungarian Antimicrobial Stewardship

Andrea Szabó^{1,2}, Mária Matuz^{1,3}, Helga Hambalek¹, Roxána Rúzsa¹, Dezső Csupor¹, Ria Benkő^{1,3}

¹ Institute of Clinical Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Szeged, Hungary

² Department of Public Health, Albert Szent-Györgyi Medical School, University of Szeged, Hungary

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global health concern that endangers the successful treatment of both human and animal diseases. Controlling antibacterial use and combating AMR necessitates collaboration between health care sectors and implementation of the One Health (OH) concept into antimicrobial stewardship (AMS). This study aimed to map the current status of AMS in Hungary with focus on the OH concept implementation.

We performed a qualitative study by conducting in-depth interviews with twelve Hungarian stakeholders from human-, animal-, and environmental sectors at ministerial, authority or hospital/university levels. The semi-structured interviews were coded by NVivo 15. Barriers and enablers of OH concept implementation were enquired.

The interviews revealed that the OH concept is in its infancy in Hungary. We are in the phase of realising and understanding the problem rather than solving it. The lack of political will is thought to be the main barrier of AMS and OH concept integration. Although OH concept is more advanced in the veterinary sector, only sporadic and non-institutionalized cooperations can be detected between the sectors. Informants also emphasized that environmental sector is highly neglected. To improve collaboration a common forum and a new responsible coordinating organization should be established according to the key informants, and implementation of the already developed national action plan is urged with dedicated financial resources.

This study was carried out within the framework of the Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance Designing One Health Governance for Antimicrobial Stewardship Interventions (DESIGN project) and supported by the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund (Hungary), grant number: 2019-2.1.7-ERA-NET.

The Role of Veterinarians in the One Health Approach to Antimicrobial Resistance Perspectives in Jordan

Randa Bazzi^{1,2,3}, Akram rishan Alaboudi⁴

¹ Faculty of Public Health, University of Debrecen, Alumni (thesis research), Debrecen, Hungary

² Greater Amman Municipality, Amman, Jordan

³ One Health Commission – FSFS, US

⁴ Jordan University of Science and Technology, Jordan

This study evaluated the role of Jordanian veterinarians in combating antimicrobial resistance (AMR) by assessing their knowledge, attitudes, and practices, and summarized registered veterinary drugs from 2017 to 2020. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect descriptive data. About 84% of participants correctly defined AMR, and 95.65% agreed that AMR is a major challenge in Jordan's veterinary sector, deserving priority over other zoonotic diseases. Around 69% believed that misuse and overuse of antimicrobials by unqualified or unauthorized practitioners is the main driver of AMR. The most common practice (80%) was advising clients to improve animal husbandry. A significant difference ($p = 0.015$) was found between AMR training attendance and the veterinarians' professional sectors (private, public, academic). The findings emphasize the need for continuous AMR education to strengthen veterinarians' knowledge and advisory roles. Enacting laws to regulate prescriptions and improving surveillance of antimicrobial use in veterinary medicine are also essential to address AMR effectively.

Antimicrobial Resistance in Wild Birds: Birds as AMR Reservoirs and Disseminators

Isma Benmazouz¹, László Kövér², Gábor Kardos^{1,3}

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² Department of Nature Conservation Zoology and Game Management, University of Debrecen, Debrecen, Hungary

³ One Health Institute, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Debrecen, Debrecen, Hungary

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) presents an urgent global health challenge, especially with the emergence of resistant strains in wildlife. Monitoring AMR in the environment, identifying potential sources, and understanding the transmission of these resistance traits among various bacterial strains in humans, domestic animals, and wildlife are critical. Utilizing the PRISMA guidelines, we conducted a comprehensive review of the global literature on AMR in wild birds, evaluating the current understanding of AMR occurrence, its geographical and temporal distribution across different bird species, and the molecular characteristics of the genetic elements identified in these birds. Our review included 296 research articles, of which 76% were published in the last decade. The majority of studies originated from Europe (53.2%) and focused on 42 different bird groups. Our findings indicated that many studies addressed resistant bacteria prioritized by the World Health Organization (WHO), with 30.7% of publications examining the genetic background of AMR. We also observed that the frequency of AMR in wild birds varied based on factors such as species sampled, study location, sample size, and specific bacterial species analyzed. However, the origins of AMR were often not discussed, and very few studies explored the potential role of wild birds in the spread of AMR. Further research is essential to clarify the precise contribution of wild birds to the environmental dissemination of AMR.

This study was funded by the Tempus Public Foundation—Stipendium Hungaricum Program, grant number: SH-00355-004/2019.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility of *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* Isolates from Canine Dermatitis in Hungary

Patrik Mag^{1,2}, Ákos Jerzsele^{1,2}

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² National Laboratory of Infectious Animal Diseases, Antimicrobial Resistance, Veterinary Public Health and Food Chain Safety, University of Veterinary Medicine Budapest, Hungary

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a major global concern, making the prudent use of antibiotics essential, especially given the slow development of new drugs. Bacterial dermatitis is the second most common diagnosis in dogs, making it a key indication for antibiotic use in companion animals. This study evaluated the efficacy of 22 antibiotics against 82 *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* isolates from canine skin infections using microdilution, including three methicillin-resistant (MRSP) strains. All isolates were susceptible to rifampicin and vancomycin. High sensitivity (>95%) was observed for oxacillin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, cefovecin, amikacin, and florfenicol. Moderate susceptibility (75–87%) was seen for cephalexin, enrofloxacin, gentamicin, sulfonamides, and ceftazidime. Lower sensitivity (<67%) was found for tetracyclines, macrolides, and clindamycin, while penicillin (37.8%) and amoxicillin (22.2%) showed the least activity. MRSP strains were only susceptible to amikacin, rifampicin, florfenicol, vancomycin, and occasionally gentamicin. Among AMEG category B fluoroquinolones, only enrofloxacin showed moderate efficacy in one case. Results suggest that amoxicillin-clavulanic acid and cephalexin remain effective first-line options for *S. pseudintermedius* skin infections, while MRSP cases may require amikacin or rifampicin. Routine susceptibility testing is critical to guide appropriate therapy and limit the spread of AMR.

Project no. RRF-2.3.1-21-2022-00001 has been implemented with the support provided by the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), financed under the National Recovery Fund budget estimate, RRF-2.3.1-21 funding scheme.

Phenotypic and Genotypic Characterization of Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) Production in Commensal *Escherichia coli* St

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The increasing spread of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL)-producing *Escherichia coli* strains poses a global public health risk. *E. coli* is a common zoonotic bacterium, and its commensal strains play a major role in antimicrobial resistance dissemination. This study aimed to examine the ESBL gene repertoire of multidrug-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from large-scale broiler and turkey flocks in Hungary, focusing on the presence of these genes on mobile genetic elements (MGEs). Initial screening was based on MIC testing (CLSI), followed by whole-genome sequencing of suspected ESBL producers. Bioinformatic analysis identified the location of resistance genes on chromosomes, plasmids, or bacteriophages and assessed their link to MGEs. Among 881 isolates, 420 were multidrug-resistant; 6% were ESBL suspects and 34% exhibited β -lactamase activity. Genotypic data showed that 55.1% of ESBL genes (CTX-M, TEM, SHV, OXA) were plasmid-borne, and 18.9% associated with MGEs. TEM was the most prevalent gene type, with variants such as TEM-1, -12, -30, -35, and -150. These findings confirm the relevance of ESBL gene carriage in poultry and its implications for public and veterinary health. The results support the importance of the One Health approach and ongoing surveillance in the poultry sector.

Project no. 2024-2.1.1-EKÖP-2024-00018 has been implemented with the support provided by the Ministry of Culture and Innovation of Hungary from the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund, financed under the 2024-2.1.1-EKÖP funding scheme. Supported by Normative Research Funding Committee (NRC), University of Veterinary Medicine Budapest. Project no. RRF-2.3.1-21-2022-00001 has been implemented with the support provided by the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), financed under the National Recovery Fund budget estimate, RRF-2.3.1-21 funding scheme.

The Role of Environmental Factors in the Spread of Antimicrobial Resistance in the Poultry Production Chain

Szilveszter Csorba^{1,2}, Krisztián Vribék^{1,2}, Máté Farkas^{1,2}, Miklós Süth^{1,2}, Orsolya Strang¹, Andrea Zentai^{1,2}, Edith Kovács^{1,3}, Zsuzsa Farkas^{1,2}

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³ Department of Analysis and Operations Research, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Budapest, Hungary

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) arises from complex health, socio-economic, environmental, and geopolitical factors, with its emergence becoming increasingly frequent. This highlights the need for tailored mitigation strategies to effectively combat the challenges posed by AMR. To minimize risks associated with AMR, it is crucial to integrate knowledge and utilize models based on extensive datasets. In our research, we examined several environmental indicators to forecast unusual changes through anomaly detection, which identifies patterns deviating from expected behavior. Furthermore, environmental factors significantly influence the development of antibiotic resistance. We employed Bayesian Network (BN) analysis to explore data structures and infer relationships among the variables. Several relevant environmental indicators were selected based on expert knowledge and existing literature. A team of experts identified the relationships among these variables. For AMR modeling, we used quantitative minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) data for Salmonella and Campylobacter, categorizing them into resistant and non-resistant groups according to predefined thresholds. Preliminary results indicated that factors such as pesticide use, fertilizer application, land use, and precipitation played crucial roles in determining resistance levels, which will inform further analyses of causal relationships.

Research funded by the National Laboratory for Infectious Animal Diseases, Antimicrobial Resistance, Veterinary Public Health and Food Chain Safety (RRF-2.3.1-21-2022-00001).

Antibiotic Resistance Patterns in Relation to Biosecurity Measures and Antibiotic Use Based on Data From Pig Farms

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Understanding the emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance (AMR) is essential for further reducing the use of antimicrobials in livestock production. The aim of this study was to explore the relationships between antibiotic usage (ABU), biosecurity practices, and AMR on pig farms using complex data analytical approach. The analyses were based on data collected from four Hungarian pig farms including antibiotic usage records (mg/kg/day) across different age groups, biosecurity parameters, clinical symptoms and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values obtained from microbiological analysis. The MIC values were determined for *E. coli* and *S. suis* isolates. AMR classification was based on EUCAST cut-off values, supplemented and revised using expert judgment. Time-series analyses were used to assess the relationship between AMR patterns and ABU data from the previous year. Gradient boosting algorithms were employed for predictive modelling, and SHAP analysis was used to interpret the influence of explanatory variables. Preliminary results indicated that lower levels of ABU were strongly associated with strict segregation of personnel and animal groups, adherence to hygiene protocols, and the use of higher-quality equipment. This research highlights the importance of proper biosecurity practices and the judicious use of antimicrobials in mitigating and can support the development of decision-support systems and future intervention strategies in the Hungarian pig sector.

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Antibiotic-resistant *Klebsiella spp.* form a Preventive Medicine Approach: a review

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Klebsiella species are of significant clinical importance, as they can cause a wide spectrum of infections varying in location and severity. They pose a major threat to public health due to increased levels of resistance to antimicrobials and their emerging role in hospital-acquired infections with high mortality rates. Extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) and carbapenemase-producing (CRE) strains, in particular, limit treatment options, especially for patients with critical medical conditions. This has prompted the World Health Organization to include *Klebsiella spp.* on the list of pathogens to be prioritized for the development of new therapies and strategies to combat antimicrobial resistance. From a preventive medicine perspective, epidemiological surveillance, infection control measures, antimicrobial stewardship programs, and alternative therapeutic approaches are essential to curbing the spread of resistant strains. Additionally, whole-genome sequencing (WGS) and next-generation sequencing (NGS) techniques provide valuable insights into the origins and transmission dynamics of resistant strains, informing more effective control measures. Alternatively, molecular biology plays a critical role in developing diagnostic tools and antibiotics targeting previously unexplored pathways.

I would like to thank my colleagues and collaborators who provided data, analysis, advice, or other significant contributions, but who are not listed as co-authors.

Investigating the Spread of Antibiotic Resistance Using Wastewater-Based Epidemiology

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In the National Centre for Public Health and Pharmacy, the detection of various antibiotic resistance genes and gene families has recently been initiated beside the investigation of the upper respiratory pathogens in the framework of wastewater-based epidemiological studies. The examinations are in line with international trends and new guidelines, as wastewater is a significant medium for the environmental spread of resistant and multi-resistant microorganisms. Each of the targets encodes resistance to antibiotics widely used in human medicine and selected because of their epidemiological importance. They are detected from DNA isolated from the remaining pellets after centrifugation of the raw wastewater samples. The primers and probes for the RT-qPCR determination of the concentrations were selected based on literature data. For quantification, copy number controls were set using of digital PCR. We used the extracted DNA of bacterias with confirmed resistance. The measurements carried out weekly, starting from week 22 of 2024, with 23 samples from wastewater treatment plants of major cities across the country, representing 40% of the country's population. The selected parameters can be detected correctly in wastewater, revealing diverse resistance profiles both in space and time. Further analysis of the measured data and comparison with clinical data may help to understand the spatial and temporal dynamics of the spread of resistance and to control it effectively.

Comparative Genomic Epidemiology of Multidrug-Resistant *Escherichia coli* Within the One Health Approach

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The spread of multidrug-resistant, ESBL-producing Enterobacterales strains is an increasing public health challenge. In our study, we investigated the occurrence and genetic epidemiology of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* isolated from the Danube River, black-headed gulls and hospitalised patients in Budapest. Whole genome sequencing was performed using the MinION platform from Oxford Nanopore Technologies. The most frequently detected resistance gene was blaCTX-M-15, which was particularly associated with human isolates of clone ST131. In contrast, environmental and avian samples showed greater genetic diversity, suggesting a broader evolutionary background and different selection pressures. The presence of similar resistance genes and plasmid patterns emphasises the importance of horizontal gene transfer and environmental persistence. Our results emphasise that effective strategies against antimicrobial resistance must go beyond the healthcare system. They require the inclusion of environmental and animal sources, which makes the implementation of the One Health approach essential.

I would like to thank the staff of the One Health Institute at the University of Debrecen and the National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy for their support.

**Section II – Emerging and Re-emerging Diseases and Vectors
Contributed Talks**

CRESS DNA Virus Surveillance in Wild Birds

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Circoviruses (CVs) are widely distributed both geographically and in terms of host species. Infections are often associated with immunosuppression, which can lead to increased susceptibility to secondary infections and may result in the death of affected animals. Besides CVs, other circular, Rep-encoding single-stranded (CRESS) DNA viruses have been detected in birds, although their significance to avian health remains unclear. The aim of our study was to assess the presence and host range of CVs and other CRESS DNA viruses in wild birds, and to genetically characterize the detected viruses. Genome sequences of CVs and circovirus-like viruses were identified in cloacal swab samples using broad-range nested PCR. Viral genomes were amplified using inverse PCR and the nucleotide sequences of the PCR products were determined by Sanger and next-generation sequencing. Out of 588 samples, the presence of CRESS DNA viruses was confirmed in 45 cases, of which 42 were verified by sequencing. So far, 12 full genome sequences were determined. Based on phylogenetic analysis, 11 genomes clustered with CVs, swan CV (n=6, mute swan), pigeon CV (n=2, peregrine falcon) and duck CV (n=1, white stork); two novel CVs were identified from long-eared owl and barn owl samples. One genome was related to members of the CRESS3 virus group. Currently, nine additional inverse PCR products are available, thus, further complete genome sequences could be obtained.

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Prevalence and Genetic Characterization of Porcine rotavirus A in Hungarian Pig Farms

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Rotaviruses (RVs) are small RNA viruses belonging to the Sedoreoviridae family and are among the most significant viral pathogens causing acute gastroenteritis in both animals and humans. The Rotavirus genus comprises nine species (A–I), classified based on the antigenic properties of the VP6 protein. The RV genome consists of 11 segments of double-stranded RNA, encoding six structural (VP) and five non-structural (NSP) proteins. RVs are considered endemic in swine populations worldwide. To assess RVA prevalence, 228 oral fluid samples were collected from 27 asymptomatic pig farms and tested by RT-qPCR. Viral RNA was detected on approximately 50% of the farms, indicating widespread subclinical circulation. For genetic characterization, 97 faecal samples were collected from 16 herds experiencing diarrhea outbreaks. Samples with high viral load were genotyped using nanopore next-generation sequencing method. VP7 genotyping identified G5, G9, and G11 types, while VP4 analysis revealed P[7], P[13], and P[23] genotypes. The most frequent G/P genotype combination was G9P[23], and in one case a full RVA genome was successfully obtained. RVA was frequently detected in co-infections with other viral and bacterial enteric pathogens, suggesting a multifactorial etiology in diarrheic piglets. These findings enhance our understanding of RVA epidemiology and evolution in Hungarian pig populations.

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Genomic Characterization of Novel Protoparvoviruses in Domestic Ruminants in Hungary

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Protoparvoviruses (Parvoviridae) are genetically diverse and infect various mammals. One protoparvovirus, Tusavirus 1, of Protoparvovirus incertum 1, was first found in humans and later in small ruminants. This study reports full coding sequences (~4600 nt) of two novel tusavirus-related protoparvoviruses from ovine ("misavirus", PV540792) and bovine ("sisavirus", PV540793) fecal samples, identified via next-generation sequencing and various PCR techniques. Their NS1, VP1, and VP2 proteins shared 61–63% amino acid identity with each other and tusaviruses (as the closest relative), suggesting misa- and sisaviruses represent two new Protoparvovirus species. Phylogenetic analyses placed them on the same branch with tusaviruses, indicating a shared origin. A small-scale epidemiological survey of 318 ruminant enteric samples using multiple primer pairs found misavirus in 14/51 (27.5%) ovine and 2/62 (3.3%) bovine, and sisavirus in 19/203 (9.4%) bovine samples. Tusavirus was present in 5/51 (9.8%) ovine and 15/62 (24.2%) caprine samples, all from one farm. All three viruses were most prevalent in animals aged 2–24 months. Phylogeny revealed virus-specific lineages and sub-lineages for misa-, sisa-, and tusaviruses, suggesting multiple genotypes. Most strains clustered by host, but two bovine sisavirus strains showed diverse placements (NS belonging to sisaviruses and VP belonging to ovine misaviruses), possibly indicating past recombination events.

We are grateful to the coworkers of the Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunology for the help conducting this research. The research was performed in collaboration with the Genomics and Bioinformatics Core Facility at the Szentágothai Research Centre of the University of Pécs. Bioinformatics infrastructure was supported by ELIXIR Hungary (<https://elixir-hungary.org>). This work was supported by the PTE ÁOK-KA No:2025/09 (University of Pécs, Medical School).

Isolation and Whole-genome Characterization of Batai virus (*Orthobunyavirus*) from a Cattle Farm in Hungary

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Among other cattle herds in Hungary a particular dairy farm was systematically sampled during the bovine viral diarrhoea virus (BVDV) eradication program. Altogether 1200 serum samples were screened for BVDV with RT-qPCR and virus was isolated for molecular genetic characterization and growth kinetic analysis. The Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) analysis (Illumina and Oxford Nanopore Technologies) of the entire RNA extracted from one virus isolate resulted in an order of magnitude more *Orthobunyavirus* reads compared to BVDV. The resulted full-length sequences of S, M and L genome segments were identified as Batai virus (BATV) belonging to the recent Euro-pean cluster. Implementing a published RT-qPCR for BATV, we examined the available serum samples from the farm, and 23 of the 1200 serum samples were positive. The BATV is a mosquito-borne *Orthobunyavirus*, which is widely found in Asia and Africa, but has also been known sporadically in Europe for decades. Confirmed cases are poorly reported. In ruminants it has been associated with some serious cases involving abortion. In human cases, however, only mild respiratory symptoms have been documented, the weak symptoms may have led to many unrecognized patients. Due to its zoonotic potential, host species should be screened revealing sources of infection, drawing the attention of both human health and veterinary professionals to the presence of BATV in Hungary.

The authors acknowledge the outstanding technical assistance of Edit Fodor and Eszter Vida (virus isolation), Viktória Sebestyén (RT-qPCR), as well as Andrea Katona and Dóra Vargáné Terebes (NGS).

Surveillance of Coronaviruses with a Novel Broad-spectrum Detection System

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Monitoring the occurrence and genomic variations of coronaviruses (CoVs) is crucial for effective containment strategies. The aim of our project was to establish a universal diagnostic system capable of broad-spectrum detection of CoVs. A PCR targeting a ~600 bp long fragment of the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase region was designed. The effectiveness of the PCR system was assessed using *in vitro* transcribed CoV RNAs, with both one-step and two-step RT, followed by (semi)nested PCR. CoV isolates from different genera and clinical samples from infected animals (NL63, OC43, SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2, porcine epidemic diarrhea virus or PEDV, transmissible gastroenteritis virus or TGEV, feline infectious peritonitis virus, canine CoV, bat CoV, infectious bronchitis virus) were used for optimization. Overall, the combination of two-step RT using touchdown cycling and random hexamers, followed by seminested PCR proved to be the most effective with a limit of detection 5-50 copies/reaction. Hundred and twenty-one nasal swab, oral fluid and processing fluid samples of swine were tested with the novel PCR system, out of which the presence of CoV was confirmed in 15 cases. Five sequences matched with porcine hemagglutinating encephalomyelitis virus, while ten showed the highest identities with porcine respiratory CoV/TGEV sequences. Apart from PEDV and TGEV, which were used during optimization of the system, the PCR system is capable of detecting another porcine virus as well.

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Tracing SARS-CoV-2 Evolution in Algeria: Insights from 2020–2023

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Understanding the regional dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 is essential for predicting future outbreaks as the world still struggles with its evolution. Algeria has experienced multiple pandemic waves, like many other nations, but little is known about its viral genomic landscape. In order to look into the evolutionary patterns, dynamics of dispersal, and adaptation of the virus in the area, we examined 449 full-length SARS-CoV-2 genomes that were gathered throughout Algeria between March 2020 and May 2023. Firstly, the phylogenetic reconstruction revealed distinct clustering patterns of the sequences despite their geographic origin, indicating multiple introductions. Complementing this, ancestral locations were traced using phylogeographic diffusion in continuous space, illustrating the diffusion of the virus across Algeria. Gene-level selection pressure analysis showed strong positive selection for the Spike gene, emphasizing its adaptive evolution, while ORF1a was subject to strong purifying selection, maintaining its function. Nine unique mutations that appear to have originated in Algeria were identified, three of which were predicted to be deleterious, indicating potential impacts on viral fitness. Finally, 179 different haplotypes were determined by haplotype network analysis. One highly interconnected star-like cluster centered around haplotype H91 suggested a superspreading event that occurred between July and September of 2022.

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Dengue Outbreaks in Northern Nigeria: Evaluating the Recommended Takeda Vaccine and Future Prevention Strategies

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Dengue fever, caused by the dengue virus (DENV), poses a significant public health challenge globally, with Nigeria experiencing sporadic outbreaks. A clear understanding of the dengue burden has not been achieved in Nigeria, just as in other African countries. Understanding the epidemiology and burden of dengue fever is essential for effective prevention and control strategies. This paper examines the recent dengue outbreaks in northern Nigeria, particularly in Sokoto state, and evaluates the recommended Takeda dengue vaccine (TDV) along with future prevention strategies. Despite limited surveillance and underreporting, dengue fever is endemic in Nigeria (with over 5 million cases and 5000 dengue related deaths in 2023), with recent outbreaks indicating a growing concern. The TDV, a live attenuated tetravalent vaccine, has shown promise in preventing dengue fever, but challenges such as vaccine acceptance and accessibility need to be addressed. Global urbanization contributes to the disease's spread, which is influenced by factors such as population density, cultural beliefs, water storage practices, hygiene, and water supply accessibility. Future prevention strategies must focus on government intervention, community practices, and innovative vector control measures to mitigate the spread of DENV in Nigeria. This study will serve as a valuable reference for policymakers, researchers, and clinicians in the management and control of DENV in Nigeria and Africa as a whole.

Blood Donors as Sentinels for Genomic Surveillance of West Nile virus in Germany

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West Nile virus (WNV) has emerged as a public health concern in Germany since its establishment in 2018. Genomic surveillance is critical for tracking viral evolution, identifying introductions, and monitoring local transmission. However, genome recovery from low-viremia samples such as those obtained through blood donor screening remains technically challenging. Our goal was to develop a sensitive targeted approach for WNV lineage 2 and apply it to low-titer samples to support genomic surveillance in Germany. A novel primer scheme was applied to 43 nucleic acid testing (NAT)-positive blood donor samples collected between 2020 and 2024. Recovered genomes were subjected to phylogenomic analysis to assess viral diversity and transmission dynamics. The amplicon protocol enabled genome recovery (>70%) from samples with viral loads as low as $\sim 10^1$ RNA copies/ μL . Of the 43 samples, 30 yielded complete or near-complete genomes. Six distinct WNV subclades (2A–2F) were identified, indicating multiple introductions into Germany from Central and Southeastern Europe. Subclade 2F emerged as the dominant and widely distributed group. Berlin, Brandenburg, Saxony, and Saxony-Anhalt were identified as persistent transmission hubs. This study highlights blood donors as a valuable sentinel population for WNV genomic surveillance. Blood donor screening in combination with molecular epidemiology provides a robust framework for early detection, transmission dynamics, and public health preparedness.

The authors would like to thank all participating blood establishments for reporting cases and providing samples of WNV-positive blood donations. We also acknowledge the regional public health authorities for their collaboration in case investigation, data provision, and support of surveillance activities during the West Nile virus transmission seasons in Germany.

Wastewater-based Epidemiological Surveillance of Respiratory Pathogens

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Wastewater analysis could provide insight into the general health status of the population. As a number of human pathogens are shed through faeces and urine, their genetic material can be detected at the wastewater treatment plant. Objective of wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) is to quantify the concentration of a certain pathogen in sewage to complement existing public health surveillance systems. Since July 2020, the Hungarian wastewater surveillance system is operated in the NCPHP, focusing on pathogens of public health relevance, including influenza A and B, as well as respiratory syncytial virus subtype B (RSV-B). 23 samples are collected on a weekly basis from wastewater treatment plants located in the capital and 18 county seats, representing approximately 40% of the Hungarian population. The samples are concentrated by ultrafiltration. After nucleic acid extraction dPCR is used for the measurement of influenza A, RT-qPCR for Influenza B and RSV-B. Influenza A has been measured weekly since January 2023, and RSV-B since January 2024. Influenza B detection was included from the 48th week of 2024 to the 20th week of 2025 in accordance with the higher incidence rate published by the Sentinel Surveillance System of the NCPHP. Data from wastewater potentially supplement the sentinel surveillance system. Using WBE, the course of an epidemic could be traced or in case of certain pathogens (e.g. Influenza A and B) even predicted.

Molecular Epidemiology of the HIV-1 Epidemic in Hungary Until 2024

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Based on routine HIV-1 drug resistance genotyping data collected since 2008, we present the most extensive molecular epidemiological analysis of the HIV-1 epidemic in Hungary to date. We analyzed partial pol sequences from 1120 Hungarian patients up to 2024, along with 2199 international sequences. We performed subtyping, drug resistance testing, maximum likelihood and Bayesian phylogenetic inference, and clustering analyses. From the Hungarian sequences, we identified 86 sequence clusters (primarily with subtypes B, A, F and CRFs). Members of larger clusters (10+ sequences) tended to be younger, more likely to be MSM, and had higher CD4 counts than patients not assigned to large clusters. Out of the seven largest transmission clusters only two MSM-dominant clusters showed substantial growth in 2023 and 2024. When incorporating international sequences, we identified 177 putative transmission clusters, 36 with at least 10 sequences. Nine were exclusively Hungarian, while 27 were mixed clusters with transmission links primarily to Western and Central Europe. Multiple independent introductions of HIV occurred in Hungary, but the epidemic has recently been driven by domestic transmission, predominantly among middle-aged MSM with a separation between MSM and heterosexual risk groups. While several large, long-lived clusters were identified, our findings suggest that the sustained incidence over the past decade is maintained by the continual emergence of new transmission clusters.

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Genome of *Aedes koreicus* and the Importance of Vector Genetics

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Vector-borne diseases pose a significant threat to human and animal welfare as well as to agriculture. An important step in understanding how these diseases spread and adapt is to study the ecological and genetic background of vector species. Among the most important vector species are haematophagous arthropods, whose range is constantly expanding due to climate change, giving arboviruses the opportunity to emerge in new areas. *Aedes koreicus* is one of the recently introduced mosquito species in Europe, including Hungary, that can transmit mosquito-borne diseases. Using a hybrid assembly approach based on next- and third-generation sequencing data, we constructed a high-quality chromosome-level genome of *Ae. koreicus* consisting of 6,099 contigs with a final size of 1.1 Gbp, an N50 value of 329,610 bp and a BUSCO score of 84%. Our annotation process identified 22,580 genes that could be functionally annotated. We also performed a direct search for potential insecticide resistance genes to contribute to the future development of methods to control mosquito populations. This genome can be the first step of a comprehensive study of the genomes of vector species in Hungary that pose a potential risk for pathogen transmission.

On behalf of the “Harmadik generációs szekvenálási adatok bioinformatikai elemzése” (Bioinformatic analysis of third generation sequencing data) projects’ team we are grateful for the possibility to use ELKH Cloud (see Héder et al. 202290; <https://science-cloud.hu/>), which helped us achieve the results published in this paper. N.A.N. was supported by the National Research, Development and Innovation Office (OTKA PD142602). The field sampling of mosquitoes and the laboratory work for the initial processing of genome data were supported by the National Research, Development and Innovation Office, Grant Numbers: FK-138563 and RRF-2.3.1-21-2022-00010 “National Laboratory of Virology.

Molecular Detection of *Anaplasma spp.* in Wild Animals in Eastern Slovakia

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Anaplasmosis is a vector-borne disease whose main vector in the Central Europe is the tick, primarily from the genus *Ixodes*. Wild animals are typical reservoirs of causative agents, as they maintain the infection in the environment. The aim of this pilot study was to investigate the prevalence of *Anaplasma spp.* in wild animals in the Eastern Slovakia. We collected a total of 86 samples from wild animals, either hunted or killed in road traffic accidents. DNA was isolated from spleen, liver, or blood clots from the heart (DNeasy® Blood & Tissue Kit - Qiagen). All samples were subsequently analyzed using a molecular method for the presence of *Anaplasma* species via nested PCR amplification of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene (546 bp). The main sample group consisted of 51 red deer (*Cervus elaphus*). Molecular detection revealed a 52.33% positivity rate, meaning 45 out of 86 samples were positive. Our findings confirm a high prevalence of *Anaplasma spp.* in the wild animal population, especially among red deer, where the prevalence reached 64.71%. The red fox population also showed a high positivity rate of 73.34% (11/15). Another positive case was detected in a Eurasian beaver. In our future study, we aim to collect more samples from a broader range of wild animals. Sequencing and phylogenetic analysis will also be among our top priorities.

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A Comprehensive Comparative Risk Analysis of Livestock Slaughterhouse Operations in Jordan and Argentina: A One Health Perspective

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Slaughterhouses serve vital public health functions through humane livestock handling, slaughtering, inspection, quality control, and waste management—each stage designed to reduce contamination risks. Veterinarians conduct ante- and post-mortem inspections to prevent zoonotic disease transmission. Modernization has improved production efficiency and hygiene, integrating risk analysis to manage physical, chemical, and biological hazards at critical points. Sustainable waste management supports environmental goals. A literature review compared food safety protocols, quality assurance, and regulations in Argentina and Jordan, showing both countries' commitment to One Health. In Argentina, meat production is a major economic sector. Of 460 registered slaughterhouses, 170 are SENASA-authorized, covering 84% of national slaughter. Federal Meat Law 22.375 and traceability systems govern the sector, though HACCP implementation remains limited in provincial facilities. In Jordan, a House risk analysis at the Greater Amman Municipality slaughterhouse identified 36 risk agents and 44 critical events. Key issues include limited slaughter space, geopolitical disruptions, poor maintenance, and transport-related contamination. These findings highlight the need for infrastructure upgrades, regulatory enforcement, and cross-sectoral collaboration to ensure safe, sustainable operations under the One Health approach."

We extend our sincere gratitude to all individuals and institutions who contributed to the success of this study. Special thanks to the Greater Amman Municipality for granting access to conduct the risk analysis at the main slaughterhouse facility in Jordan. We also acknowledge the valuable insights and data provided by the National Agri-Food Health and Quality Service (SENASA) in Argentina.

Section III – Food Safety and Foodborne Diseases
Contributed Talks

Advancing Biofungicide Strategies to Ensure Healthy Crop Production

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Fungal pathogens pose a significant threat to sustainable agriculture, often resulting in substantial crop losses. In response to the limitations of conventional chemical fungicides, particularly in crops with physical barriers to absorption, there is growing interest in the development of plant-based biofungicides. Natural plant extracts offer a promising alternative due to their bioactive compounds and potential to trigger plant defence mechanisms. This study focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of selected plant extracts in enhancing disease resistance and promoting plant health. By examining different formulations, including innovative delivery systems, we aim to identify effective strategies for controlling fungal infections through natural means. The findings contribute to the advancement of environmentally friendly plant protection solutions and support the broader application of biofungicides in crop production.

This work was funded by the KFI_16-1-2017-0457 project titled "Development and production of a plant-based pesticide-plant conditioner for use in organic farming."

Inhibition of *Botrytis cinerea* Mycelial Growth by Soluble and Volatile Metabolite and Plant Promoting Activity in Tomatoes Seed

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Botrytis cinerea, is considered the second most important plant pathogen with devastating economic impact on different crops, including tomato. *Trichoderma afroharzianum* (TR04) is a promising biocontrol agent against fungal plant pathogens. *Trichoderma* species are successful antagonists having biocontrol abilities against economically important plant parasitic soil-borne pathogens and present abundantly in almost all type of soils. *Trichoderma* exhibit antagonistic behavior against several phytopathogenic organisms by indirect mechanism or direct mechanism such as antibiosis. This research evaluates its antifungal activity against *B. cinerea*, its growth promoting effects on tomato seeds, and its salt tolerance. The results indicate that *T. afroharzianum* (TR04) produces both volatile and non-volatile metabolites exhibiting antifungal properties. Specifically, the culture filtrate suppressed *B. cinerea* growth by 14.73%, non-volatiles with 10.30%, and volatiles with 15.76%. In growth promotion assays, *T. afroharzianum* (TR04) metabolites did not significantly enhance tomato seed growth except for reducing primary root length compared to the control. Notably, *T. afroharzianum* (TR04) exhibited robust growth under salt stress conditions (0.5M, 0.75M, and 1.25M NaCl), although its morphology changed significantly, displaying yellow sporulation instead of the typical green.

I would like to extend my deepest appreciation to the Institute of Food Science for providing the necessary resources, academic support, and conducive environment that facilitated the successful development of these essays.

The Importance of Biosecurity Measures in Cyprinid Fish Ponds: the Preliminary Results from Bosnia and Herzegovina

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Due to the presence of infectious diseases in aquaculture, the development of biosecurity programs that prevent, control, and eradicate diseases in aquaculture operations plays a more important role. Based on the actual official data from the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina, the total production of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) fish ponds in 2023 was only 123,3 tons, based on the facilities of the surface 2.042 ha. Generally, the literature sources about fish health monitoring (incl. biosecurity measures) on the cyprinid fish ponds in Bosnia and Herzegovina are scarce. It was a reason to arrange screening investigations to check staff knowledge and the implementation of biosecurity principles are present on 4 cyprinid fish farms. Our research assessed aquaculture production in the following municipalities: Derventa, Prnjavor, Brod and Bileca. The study included a survey with fish farm production managers and the use of a questionnaire with 15 questions on important parameters, i.e. the written biosecurity plan, cleaning & washing protocol and disinfection protocol. Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that in the majority of fish farms, the knowledge and realisation of the basic principles of biosecurity measures are at a low level and that there is a big space for improvement of the current status. It means to continue education and assessment of biosecurity measures, including the design of specific protocols for each farm.

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Foodborne Pathogens in Cheese: Their Origins, Risks, and One Health Relevance

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The microbiological quality and food safety of cheese begins with the milk. Milk represents an excellent medium for various microorganisms. Milk of good microbiological quality with low bacterial counts is essential to achieve optimal cheese yield, quality and food safety. Many microorganisms can contaminate cheese during production and ripening, leading to further defects, quality and food safety problems. In general, foodborne illness associated with cheese is primarily associated with soft cheeses or raw milk cheeses. The most common foodborne pathogenic bacteria associated with cheese consumption are *Listeria monocytogenes*, enteropathogenic *E. coli*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Staphylococcus aureus*. In our recent studies, we have examined the prevalence of microorganisms important from a food safety perspective in different types of artisanal and industrial cheeses (EU Commission Regulation 2073/2005/EC on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs) according to ISO standards. The most abundant bacterial species were identified on the basis of 16S rDNA sequences. To avoid bacterial contamination, compliance with general hygiene procedures is essential. Staff must be in good health. Equipment should be in good physical and microbiological condition. Adherence to appropriate production parameters is essential, as pathogenic microorganisms can proliferate in products sensitive to temperature or pH increases.

Multi-Element Profiling and Health Risk Assessment of Commercial Tahini Products using ICP-OES

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Tahini, a widely consumed plant-based spread made from sesame seeds, is appreciated for its rich nutritional profile. Yet, concerns over toxic metal accumulation in this product have emerged, especially with increasing global trade. In this study, 20 elements were analyzed in 22 tahini samples from diverse regions (Syria, Jordan, Egypt, Palestine, Germany) using ICP-OES. Particular attention was given to As, Pb, Al, Ni, and Ba, for which dietary risk was evaluated by estimating daily intake (EDI) and calculating the target hazard quotient (THQ), based on a 20 g/day consumption rate and a 50 kg body weight. Findings showed that As posed a potential chronic risk, with a THQ of 1.35, surpassing the reference dose set by IRIS. Pb levels reached up to 2.073 mg/kg, raising concern due to cumulative toxicity, despite the absence of an official RfD. In contrast, Al, Ni, and Ba displayed lower THQs (0.55, 0.45, and 0.23 respectively), suggesting acceptable levels under typical intake. Variations most likely influence the differences observed between samples in soil composition, water quality, and processing methods. These results highlight the importance of managing environmental and production-related contamination to minimize exposure to foodborne toxins. Ensuring stricter quality control and monitoring, particularly in tahini destined for export, can play a key role in preventing chronic health effects and enhancing the overall safety of sesame-based products.

Investigation of the Soaking of Matured Semi-hard Cheeses in Blackcurrant Wine or in Natural Blackcurrant Juice

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Knowing that cheeses and red berries and the wines made from them are so beneficial effects of these and all the many varieties of wine, our aim was to combine these benefits with high nutritional value and non-traditional properties, which could broaden the range of special cheeses. The soaking effect of matured semi-hard cheeses in blackcurrant wine and natural juice were investigated by determination of antioxidant capacity, microbiological and antioxidant properties of the rheological and organoleptic properties. To characterise the antioxidant capacity, three methods were used to determine the total polyphenol content by Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, carried out an iron reduction capacity method (FRAP), and the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical method. The main anthocyanins of blackcurrant were also determined by HPLC. The microbiological tests were carried out to determine the potentially pathogenic bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*), moulds, yeasts, and lactic acid bacteria, by culture. The organoleptic properties of the cheese were measured during soaking with the RGB colour detector phone app, and the changes in texture were rheological tests were performed using an Anton Paar rheometer. Taste of the products focus group tasting was conducted to determine the taste of the products using a 0-10 point rating scale.

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Risk Factors for Spinach Consumption and How to Improve Them

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Spinacia oleracea L. consumption is becoming increasingly popular due to its beneficial health effects and its usability. It can be harvested several times a year, as it is a cold-tolerant plant. However, spinach can be linked to several food safety risks. Foodborne illnesses are significant and increasingly common problems worldwide. From 2014 to 2021, 2028 illnesses, 477 hospitalizations and 18 deaths related to leafy green vegetables were reported by CDC. The most common pathogen bacteria in fresh products such as Spinach, are pathogenic *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *Salmonella spp.*, *Enterobacter spp.*, *Citrobacter spp.*, *Shigella spp.* and *Listeria monocytogenes*. In order to prevent foodborne illnesses related to spinach and minimize food safety risks, we need food safety measures such as careful purchasing, storage under appropriate conditions, and effective washing procedures. Among of washing processes these are many attempt with different results and effect on human health. In a previous study we investigated the effect of washing with citric acid for the shelf life parameters of spinach. Washing spinach with 0.5% citric acid solution preserved leaf elasticity, slightly affected chlorophyll content, reduced *E. coli* and yeast/mold counts for up to four days, but did not significantly decrease total bacterial count, suggesting the need for further optimization to improve microbial safety without compromising quality.

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Effect of Chitosan Coating on Healthy and Infected Walnuts

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Walnut (*Juglans regia* L.) is globally valued for its nutritional richness and economic significance, driving research into its chemical properties. This study investigated the effect of chitosan coating on Hungarian walnuts. Impact was evaluated on healthy walnuts (KOKO – control, KOKI – with chitosan), symptomatic ones (TEKI, TEKO), and walnuts inoculated with *Penicillium* (PEKO, PEKI). The aim was to assess nutritional attributes and potential food applications. After 3 months of storage, dry matter ranged from 94.16% (PEKI) to 96.02% (TEKI), with KOKI (95.91%) showing consistency. Lipid content ranged from 63.45% (KOKO) to 65.37% (TEKI), confirming energy density. Total polyphenol content (TPC), in mg gallic acid equivalent/100g, peaked in KOKI (410.11 mg) and was lowest in PEKO (365.92 mg). Flavonoid content, as mg catechin equivalent/100g, was highest in TEKO (273.37 mg) and lowest in PEKI (181.52 mg). Elemental analysis showed high potassium (3666.00 ppm), phosphorus (2768.67 ppm), and boron (9.71 ppm) in PEKI and PEKO, while TEK I had the most copper (8.11 ppm) and magnesium (582.27 ppm). Absence of toxic elements confirms safety. Findings suggest chitosan-treated TEK I and KOKI suit antioxidant-rich products, TEKO for flavonoid-focused foods. PEKI and PEKO may suit dense formulations. KOKO's uniformity supports standardized production, while PEKI's variability indicates a need for improved processing.

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Designing Novel Plant-based Cheese-like Product Using Walnuts: Insights from Color and Texture Parameters

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Plant-based diets are primarily driven by a growing awareness of concerns related to health, sustainability issues, and the ethical treatment of animals. This study aimed to design and optimize a plant-based cheese-like product from walnuts and to gain insights into its potential as dairy cheese alternative. Development and optimization of the walnut cheese-like product were conducted applying response surface methodology. The experimental design assessed the effects of three independent variables: walnuts/water ratio (1/13.3 – 1/2.56), walnut oil content (11.6 – 18.4%) and instant yeast amount (1.2 – 2.8%). Texture characteristics of cheese-like formulations were determined using a texture analyzer TA.HDplusC coupled with probe P/5S and $\varnothing = 5$ mm. Formulations with higher walnuts/water ratio and instant yeast amount had slightly decreased lightness L and b*, as well as increased a* parameter. The Pearson correlations were determined to reveal the contribution of three independent variables to all evaluated parameters of plant-based cheese-like product. The heatmap diagram proved strong correlations of color (L, a*, b*) characteristics with texture parameters (hardness, adhesiveness, springiness, cohesiveness, gumminess), predicting that evaluated parameters were closely associated with walnuts/water ratio, walnut oil and instant yeast content. The implication of these results are significant for advancing walnut kernel potential within the plant-based cheese-like industry.

The research was supported by Institutional Project, subprogram 020405 “Optimizing food processing technologies in the context of the circular bioeconomy and climate change”, Bio-OpTehPAS, being implemented at the Technical University of Moldova.

Plant-based Yoghurt: a Promising Sustainable Alternative to Dairy Products

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Prevailing food trend in the dairy industry is the demand to develop various plant-based alternatives to dairy products. The aim of this study was the optimization and validation of plant-based yoghurt formula using STAT-EASE 360 software. All formulations with different amount of pectin, emulsifier and ratio of walnuts/water (used for walnut milk development) were inoculated with commercial cultures. Measured responses included physicochemical parameters, antioxidant potential and sensory attributes of all plant-based yoghurt alternative formulations. The primary factor affecting ($P < 0.05$) all the responses was the walnut/water ratio used for walnut milk preparation. The product optimisation carried out maximising the quality properties indicated that best formulation to obtain plant-based formulation was pectin amount of 1.50%, emulsifier amount of 0.10% and walnuts/water ratio 1/2.56. The phenolic profile of plant-based yoghurt attested total polyphenol content of 257 mg GA/100g and total flavonoids content of 93 mg QE/100g. Optimized formulation increased the in vitro DPPH and ABTS antioxidant activity in comparison with reference sample. Although optimized formula had an effect on the color characteristics (L , a^* , b^*), a significant difference in the sensory scores was not recorded by panelists. Optimized formulation had high scores on all sensory attributes (≥ 8.15). The results of this research are an important step in developing future food products.

The research was supported by Institutional Project, subprogram 020405 "Optimizing food processing technologies in the context of the circular bioeconomy and climate change", Bio-OpTehPAS, being implemented at the Technical University of Moldova.

Using Management Approaches and Plant-based Feed Supplements in Large-scale Pig Farms as Alternative Solutions to Weaning

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With stricter regulation of using antibiotics and zinc oxide, post-weaning diarrhoea became a common problem for pig farms. Weaning diarrhoea sometimes cause increase in mortality rates, but the greatest economic loss happens because of the reduced FCR and ADG. The banning of zinc oxide, despite regulation, increased the use of some antibiotics which are also important in human medicine. The high amount and possibly inappropriate use of these antibiotics significantly increases the risk of resistance. This presentation will summarise the management factors which, according to the literature, may have a significant impact on the development of post-weaning diarrhoea. My research aims to assess the level of the problem on 10 large scale pig farms, which of the relevant management options identified in the literature are being applied and with what effectiveness. In this study, rectal swab samples will be taken from animals affected by the disease. From the samples we will do bacteriological analysis and resistance tests. Several alternative feed-additives are available on the market, but none has yet been able to replace zinc oxide alone. Part of the research is to develop a plant-based feed supplement with Bata Ltd., that could be a suitable alternative to zinc oxide.

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Effectiveness of Food Safety Self-checking Systems in Hungarian School Catering

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Food safety inspections in production units are essential for maintaining standards. Inspections include self-checking by employees, internal and external audits, and official inspections. Many European countries mandate or recommend self-checking alongside HACCP systems, yet official inspections still reveal food safety issues, questioning their effectiveness. Our research examined the ability of self-checking systems to identify food safety risks in food production. Over four months, we surveyed ten institutional catering kitchens using a checklist completed by catering managers, internal auditors, and external auditors. The data from these checklists were compared to assess discrepancies. External auditors consistently rated food safety factors lower than internal auditors and catering managers. The greatest inconsistencies appeared in personal hygiene, storage processes, and sanitation. These findings indicate that food handlers tend to overestimate compliance, leaving many risks undetected. Therefore, external audits and official inspections remain crucial.

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CONTEMFOOD Project: Contaminants in Meat Replacement Products: A Contemporary Food Safety Perspective

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The CONTEMFOOD project, led by the University of Veterinary Medicine Budapest, launching on January 1, 2025, will "put on the table" the chemical food safety aspects of modern foods, particularly alternative meat substitutes. The project will investigate the presence of processing contaminants such as carcinogenic and mutagenic acrylamide, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and metals in commercially available and frequently consumed meat substitute products. Researchers will conduct the analyses in Hungary, Sweden, and Portugal, providing a comprehensive picture of contaminant levels across different European regions. The selected meat substitutes will be examined for processing contaminants based on their preparation methods as well. In addition to the analyses, the project will develop a database containing data and information on contaminants found in meat substitutes. This database will encompass both the data generated by the project and publicly available contaminant data. A knowledge graph based on the database will also be developed, facilitating the understanding and processing of relationships between contaminants, food types, and food safety aspects using modern network analysis and visualization tools. The results will be crucial in addressing the information gaps in this new field, contributing to the safety of modern foods and, consequently, to the protection of consumer health amidst changing dietary trends and environmental challenges.

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Recent Research Efforts on the Detection of Agrochemicals in Honey and Honey Products in Kenya

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Bees collect Agrochemicals from flowering vegetation, which are deposited in honey and honey products, causing a health risk. Data from Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, and other scientific databases were screened to determine type of Honeybee product contaminated, type and group of the agrochemical detected, source of samples, methods for identifying and quantifying agrochemical residues, based on European Union (EU) maximum residue limits (MRLs) to evaluate safety. Honey, pollen (Bee bread), and wax had agrochemicals. Bee bread consistently had the highest levels. Thiamethoxam in Bee bread exceeded acceptable levels in Thika. Insecticides, fungicides, acaricides, and degradation products were confirmed in at least 21 locations in Kiambu, Nairobi, Muranga, and Taita. Transmara had no detectable levels. Samples were from apiaries, supermarkets and local retail shops. The methods of analysis were ultra-high performance chromatography and liquid chromatography mass spectrometry. Most agrochemicals were below the limits of quantification and maximum residue limit; however, Acetamiprid ($1202.50 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) (EU limit ($50 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)), chlorpyrifos, and malathion (0.092 mg/kg) (Limit 0.05 mg/kg) were above MRLs. There is an urgent need to enforce pesticide regulation, improve the existing guidelines on agrochemical use and regular screening of honeybee products.

Key words: Agrochemicals, honey, bees, Kenya pollinators

We wish to acknowledge the kind help from Douglas Mwirigi for the support in accessing research articles used in our study.

Evaluating the Antimicrobial Properties of Purslane (*Portulaca oleracea* L.) Extracts Against Clinically Relevant Pathogens

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Purslane (*Portulaca oleracea* L.) is commonly known as a weed, although it is a medically useful plant consumed as food worldwide. Purslane's therapeutic value comes from its rich bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, terpenoids, omega-3s, vitamins and minerals. It has antioxidant, antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, liver-protective, and antidiabetic effects both in vitro and in vivo. Notably, the plant's methanolic and ethanolic extracts have synergistic effects with conventional antibiotics against some multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens, such as *Staphylococcus aureus*. Due to its strong antioxidant activity, it can also protect tissues from oxidative stress. Proper preparation and heat treatment enhance the effectiveness and preservation of purslane's active ingredients. We aim to produce purslane extracts from purslane leaves grown under greenhouse conditions and investigate the antimicrobial properties, which we will test on various bacteria. During the experiment, we would like to determine which extract is most effective against pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* or *Enterococcus faecalis*. Purslane is a safe, affordable option for antimicrobial and complementary therapies, especially in developing countries. Its wide-ranging benefits warrant further research for use in functional foods, dietary supplements and future medical/pharmaceutical applications.

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Pseudocereals in Beer Production: Investigation of Quality, Nutritional Value and Chemical Safety

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In this study, buckwheat, red and white sorghum and millet were tested as primary ingredients of brewing. After malting these pseudocereals, ales were produced from each with the same technology. Antioxidant and element content, colour, acidity and bitterness of the samples were measured to assess the applicability of pseudocereals to provide options of beer consumption for consumers suffering from celiac disease. Furthermore, a risk assessment was carried out regarding the presence of toxic elements. Based on the results, buckwheat beer was the richest in antioxidant compounds, while other samples contained about 50% of traditional ales' phenolic content. In contrast, our gluten-free products contained slightly higher amounts of flavonoids than barley beers. Bitterness and acidity of the samples were corresponding to the beer type, however, colour of them was darker than expected. Despite buckwheat's high macro element content, buckwheat beer was the richest only in potassium and sulphur, while its sodium content was low. Sorghum beers contained the highest amount of micro elements. Probably, elemental composition was influenced by the fermentation process too. None of the analysed toxic elements pose risk to the consumers. Quality parameters of these gluten-free products are similar to commercial beers, buckwheat beers are rich in antioxidants, and element content of the beverages may be beneficial. However, technological difficulties might occur during their production.

We would like to express our gratitude to every individual who supported us carrying this project out.

**Section IV – Alternatives to Antimicrobials in Human and Veterinary
Medicine**

Contributed Talks

Bacteriophages Against Antibiotic-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Strains

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Klebsiella pneumoniae is an important nosocomial pathogen with decreased antibiotic susceptibility; extended spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) and/or carbapenemase producers are frequently detected in clinical samples. In these infections, bacteriophages may be used as an alternative treatment option. After the demonstration of ESBL and/or carbapenemase production, bacteriophages were isolated from wastewater samples. Drop agar method was used to determine the host spectrum of phages and their stability after a three month-long storage at 4 °C, -20 °C and -80 °C. Cross activity test was performed on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus gallolyticus*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Escherichia coli*. 229 bacteriophage isolates were separated against our *K. pneumoniae* strains; all but two strains were sensitive to at least three phage suspensions. In cross test, phages did not show activity against abovementioned bacteria and the storage at different temperatures did not decrease their activity. In conclusion, high number of phages was isolated for multiresistant *K. pneumoniae* strains and the cross test demonstrated their strict host species specificity, and isolated phages remained active after long-term storage. To determine whether broad spectrum phages or a phage mixture is responsible for the damage of multiple bacterial strains, ultracentrifugation will be performed and sequence analysis of target bacterial strains as well as isolated phages are also planned.

I would like to thank all the staff at One Health Institute, who helped me with my lab work.

Isolation and Characterization of *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* Infecting Bacteriophages

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Stenotrophomonas maltophilia, a Gram-negative multidrug-resistant nosocomial pathogen, has natural resistance to most antibiotics; therefore, alternative therapeutic agents such as bacteriophages may be of particular importance. We screened 23 sewage water samples from Budapest, Hungary for phages against different strains of *S. maltophilia*. We performed phage detection using the spot method. We isolated and sequenced separate phages' genomic DNA using Oxford Nanopore sequencing. After careful filtering and de novo assembly, we selected the high-quality genome assemblies for further bioinformatic analyses, including predictions of gene function, host and lifestyle, and taxonomic classification. As a result, we present genomic data of 34 bacteriophages capable of infecting *S. maltophilia*. The isolated phages, which were all virulent, had a dsDNA genome with a length of 38 to 72 kb. We could not detect any bacterial resistance genes or virulence factors in the phage genomes. Taxonomic classification revealed that All of the bacteriophage belong to realm Duplodnaviria, kingdom Heunggongvirae, phylum Uroviricota and class Caudoviricetes. Nine phages belong to Autographiviridae and one into Drexelvriidae family. Twenty-four samples could not be classified at family level. Presented phages infecting *S. maltophilia* could be considered for therapeutic intervention.

Coworkers of Institute of Metagenomics and One Health.

Section V – Social Perceptions of Antibiotics and Their Alternatives
Contributed Talks

AI-Supported Discourse Analysis of Vaccine Skepticism in a Post-Truth Context

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In an era frequently described as “post-truth”—a label used to characterize contexts where personal beliefs and emotions heated by online discourses often override objective facts—, vaccine skepticism poses a significant challenge to public health communication. In Hungary, over 5,000 health visitors serve as frontline professionals, counseling parents on child immunization amid a landscape influenced by online misinformation and conspiracy theories. The current study, which is part of a broader research project that employs both qualitative and quantitative methods to address the phenomenon of vaccine skepticism, focuses on a critical discourse analysis of online vaccine-skeptical narratives. For our study, we gathered anonymised data through scraping social media contributions shared by users, mainly in YouTube comment streams, complemented by posts on X and Reddit, and employed thematic analysis using generative AI, manual coding and thematic analysis in Nvivo. The study aims to uncover the argumentation strategies, emotional appeals, and misinformation tactics prevalent in Hungarian vaccine-hesitant and anti-vaccine online communities. The insights derived from this analysis will inform the design of quantitative survey instruments and will be also translated into evidence-based communication recommendations. Ultimately, this research contributes to the development of inclusive and culturally sensitive messaging strategies for health visitors.

Behavioural Drivers of Hand Hygiene: Early Results from the EU JAMRAI 2 WP7.4 Hungarian Pilot Study Using the COM-B Model

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The National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy (NNGYK) represents Hungary as the competent authority in the EU JAMRAI 2 Joint Action, which brings together experts from 30 European countries to prevent and reduce healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial resistance. Within this European collaboration, the international WP7.4 work package focuses on promoting the use of behavioural science tools at various levels of the healthcare system to support everyday infection control practices—such as improving healthcare workers' hand hygiene compliance. Pilot studies based on the COM-B model explore the individual, organisational, and cultural factors influencing specific behaviours (e.g. hand hygiene compliance or non-compliance). These findings inform the development and implementation of interventions that support positive behaviour change. The COM-B framework highlights three key components influencing behaviour: Capabilities, Opportunities, and Motivation. In the context of hand hygiene, these relate to physical and psychological ability, external (material and social) enablers or barriers, and internal processes such as habits, beliefs, and attitudes. The Hungarian pilot study is coordinated by NNGYK in collaboration with two partner hospitals and experts in infection control, behavioural science, and sociology. The present paper discusses the first results of the survey and interview research, analysed using nVivo software and the framework analysis method.

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Left Behind in Health: The Consequences of Digital Disconnection and Limited Support

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Efforts to control the spread of infectious diseases and mitigate antimicrobial resistance require not only biomedical interventions but also a socially embedded understanding of how individuals access and process health-related information. This study explores how digital exclusion and the absence of interpretative support contribute to hidden vulnerabilities in health literacy, which may undermine timely responses to infectious threats. Using data from our representative panel survey (N=500), we examined the frequency with which individuals report difficulties in understanding their own health status and whether they receive assistance in interpreting medical information such as hospital documentation. Our findings reveal that respondents without any internet access or those who never receive help with understanding health-related materials are overwhelmingly likely to report “never” experiencing difficulties. This paradox points to a latent lack of awareness, rather than competence, indicating a form of informational vulnerability that is not self-recognized. Such structural disadvantages highlight the critical importance of addressing social and digital inequalities within infection prevention strategies. Empowering individuals through equitable access and interpretative support is essential for achieving effective, population-level health communication and responsiveness.

Professional guidance of Rusinné Dr. Fedor Anita.

Towards Responsible Antibiotic Use: Progress Report on a Participatory Research Project in Primary Care

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In early 2025, two participatory workshops were held in Hungary to explore how patients, general practitioners, and other stakeholders perceive and shape decisions around antibiotic use in primary care. Using storytelling, role-playing, and backcasting, participants co-created fictional characters and future scenarios to model doctor-patient interactions and map pathways toward more responsible antibiotic practices. Workshop discussions, co-created materials, and facilitator observations were analyzed using thematic analysis with NVivo 12 software. Results highlight structural barriers such as limited consultation time, patient expectations influenced by commercial messaging, and low trust in the healthcare system. At the same time, participants identified key enablers, including empathetic communication, shared decision-making, and simple educational tools. The study demonstrates how participatory methods can generate practical insights for policies that promote more effective and sustainable antibiotic use.

Sequencing Method Optimized for Monitoring Microbiome Changes in Burn Patients

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Burn injury is a complex trauma that can range from minor wounds to systemic pathological conditions. Severe burns covering over 20% of an adult's body trigger systemic inflammation, generating free radicals and oxidative stress. This stress disrupts the gut microbiome, causing bacterial dysbiosis characterized by decreased diversity and dominance of pathogenic strains, leading to endogenous infections. Our research aimed to optimize a 16S sequencing method to examine gut microbiome changes after severe burns. Samples from seven patients, collected at various times with replicates, were used to test method reliability. DNA was extracted, diluted, amplified by 16S rDNA PCR, verified by gel electrophoresis, purified, barcoded, pooled, and sequenced. Taxa identification and comparisons revealed significant variation due to sampling times and patient differences. Genus diversity ranged from 22 to 123, with *Bacteroides* and *Blautia* being the most common genera. The method proved reproducible, as two out of three replicates showed consistent results, supporting the reliability of the protocol.

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Anaphylactic Reaction Secondary to Surgically Treated Hydatid Cyst: a Case Report

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In medical practice, it is not uncommon to encounter cases of hydatid disease (echinococcosis), where cysts are incidentally discovered in various organs or present secondary to spontaneous or accidental rupture. These ruptures may have unknown causes but are often triggered by trauma, medical interventions, or iatrogenic factors, particularly during or after surgery. The intervention was complicated by cyst rupture and the onset of immediate anaphylactic shock. Over time, this led to the development of new secondary hydatid cysts in other organs, particularly in the lungs and liver. It is important to note that the patient had received appropriate antiparasitic prophylaxis with Albendazole, both before and after the surgical procedure. However, despite adherence to antiparasitic therapy, secondary dissemination still occurred, underscoring the necessity of strict adherence to surgical protocols in such cases. In conclusion, this case highlights the risk of systemic dissemination and severe allergic reactions even in patients under antiparasitic treatment, and reinforces the importance of careful surgical planning and post-operative monitoring in echinococcosis cases. This case highlights the potential immunological complications associated with echinococcal cyst rupture or manipulation during surgical procedures. Clinical presentation, management, and outcomes are discussed to raise awareness of this potentially life-threatening complication.